

UNDERSTANDING PROFESSIONAL IDENTITY OF FUTURE TEACHERS AS A PEDAGOGICAL - PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEM

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Abstract: This article describes the problems that arise in the realization of the professional identity of future teachers and their solutions.

Key words: future teacher, pedagogue, pedagogical skills, knowledge, skills, abilities.

In today's globalized era, many measures are being developed by our state in order to mature young people who have new thinking, creative thinking and abilities, and all of these are based on the level of education, science and technology, and pedagogical skills. It is necessary to find out early on which profession the child has interest and ability, and to which profession his character-characteristics correspond, and show him the right direction in time. The advantage of identifying a child's ability early and guiding him in the right direction is that he will grow up to be a mature member of his profession. If we show the good sides of the profession he is interested in to the child from a young age, his interest in this profession will increase. Therefore, if the child is shown the right way from the beginning and given the right education, the future teacher will not have any problems in realizing his professional self, even if he comes with the knowledge he has received, based on his skills and abilities, he quickly finds a solution to it.

However, it should not be forgotten that it is not enough to love one's profession and have enough knowledge and skills, a person must also have well-developed cognitive processes suitable for the profession. For example, if we take the profession of teaching, no matter how much the knowledge of the pedagogue is sufficient, if he is not good at speech activity from cognitive processes, if he cannot fully express his thoughts, that is, even if he has little vocabulary, he is mature in his profession. cannot be a frame. Therefore, in order to help future teachers to understand their professional identity in the higher education system, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 21.06.2022, No. PQ-289 on measures ", starting from the 2022-2023 academic year, weekly training sessions for students of the 2nd-4th stage of full-time education will be "4+2", i.e. 4 days of classes will be held in higher education institutions, and 2 days will be in general secondary educational

institutions. was introduced. This means that the future teachers are gaining knowledge and skills by using their theoretical knowledge in the subjects in practice.

The interpretation of the future teacher's personal professional self-study in certain pedagogical-psychological conditions serves as an initial theoretical basis and table. The professional reflection of the future teacher can be developed on the basis of individualization of the educational process of higher pedagogical educational institutions.

VA-Krivoshev, who studied communicative and personal reflection, said that as a teacher acquires pedagogical skills in his work, he begins to better understand what his colleagues and students think about him, deep acquired knowledge and pedagogical due to the skill, the teacher begins to evaluate himself. The author concludes that communicative reflection determines the content, system and uniformity of personal reflection.

Summary

In today's rapidly developing era of science and technology, the teacher must be ready for new modern education, because new different methods and technologies are being developed every day, which requires strong knowledge, skills and competence from the teacher of today . is enough. It is necessary to master these methods and technologies and be able to use them effectively in a wide range of activities.

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